

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

PSEUDONYMITY

USER GUIDE

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Pseudonymity Client: User Guide

Usage

The pseudonymity client tool is used as follows: `pseudo-cert-request --url <service-url> [options]`

Command-line Options

Property	Description	Required?	Default Value
-a, --truststore <filename>	absolute pathname to the truststore	N	None
-b, --truststorePwd <password>	password protecting the truststore	N	None
-c, --cadir <directory>	absolute pathname to the directory for the CA files	N	/etc/grid-security/certificates
-D, --storedir <directory>	absolute pathname to the store directory	N	~/globus
-h, --help	prints the help screen	N	
-k, --keypass <password>	password protecting the new private key	N	None
-n, --nocrl	avoids certificate revocation check	N	
-P, --prefix <prefix>	prefix for the pseudocert.pem and pseudokey.pem	N	None
-p, --proxyfile <filename>	absolute pathname to the proxy file	N	/tmp/x509up_u
-s, --keysize <size >	key strength for the new keypair	N	1024
-u, --url <service-url>	url for the pseudonymity server's login endpoint	Y	None
-v, --verbose	displays more information about the sequence	N	
-V, --version	displays the version information	N	

Example scenario and output

The following example requests a pseudonymous credentials from the service at `https://pseudo-example.cern.ch:8443/pseudo/Login` by using the proxy file at `/tmp/x509up_u1000`.

```
pseudo-cert-request --url https://pseudo-example.cern.ch:8443/pseudo/Login -p /tmp/x509up_u1000 -
pseudo-cert-request: org.glite.pseudo.ui.PseudoInit - Copyright (c) 2011. Members of the EMI Coll
```

```
ServiceUrl: https://pseudo-example.cern.ch:8443/pseudo/Login
New Key Password: changeit
Retype: changeit
Proxy Filename: /tmp/x509up_u1000
Connecting to the pseudonymity service ... ok
Generating a public/private keypair (1024 bit) ... ok
Submitting the certificate request ... ok
```

```
Pseudo certificate (/root/.globus/pseudocert.pem) expires on 'Fri Apr 25 08:50:37 CEST 2014'.
```

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